

INTERACTION AND EXPLOITATION OF SYNERGIES

The direction to modernized and more competitive R&I systems is the way towards the competitiveness improvement in Greece and Portugal relying on the development of high added value innovative products and services with a strong societal footprint.

DemosAxia maximizes the added value and impact of projects IMOCO4.E and GRAPHEYE, including their platforms, networks, associations, and other initiatives consisting of identifying and leveraging the resources and creating new sources of value that form the base for building synergy.

RESEARCH-INDUSTRY JOINT ACTIVITIES

Increase the outreach of potential stakeholders by organize joint events, exchange knowledge, experience, and best practices, and stimulate discussions among key players.

